

Large Language Models for Digital Foundational Identity

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Large language models (LLMs) represent a groundbreaking development in the artificial intelligence (AI) domain, capable of ingesting textual data and generating coherent text outputs [Bommasani et al. \(2022\)](#). These models have ushered in a transformative era in AI, showcasing their effectiveness across an extensive array of applications. Their remarkable success has been observed in diverse sectors such as healthcare, law, and education [Kaddour et al. \(2023\)](#). Nonetheless, the extent of their impact within the realm of digital identity remains underexplored. In light of this, this paper delves into potential use cases for LLMs in the digital identity space, drawing inspiration from the insights gleaned from ID4D reports [World Bank \(2022\)](#), which highlight the specific needs and requirements in this identity domain.

Identity

Identity (ID) is a complex and multi-component construct with strong cultural and societal values [Council of Europe \(2023\)](#). It is also the gateway to accessing vital public services such as enrolling on the education system, healthcare and accessing social benefits. The basic role of an ID system is answering three questions [World Bank Group \(2019\)](#): (1) Who are you? (Identification), (2) Are you who you claim to be? (Authentication), (3) Are you authorized/eligible? (Authorization) Based on purposes, governments generally have two types of ID systems: Foundational (National ID) and functional (Driver license, voter register, etc.). Foundational identity defines the main characteristics of an individual's identity such as name, sex, place and date of birth. This identity is mostly issued by an authorized civil registration authority following the occurrence of birth. In some cases, the birth registration might be missed and the citizen should claim their identity with documents or trusted authorities. For a functioning foundational identity system, the civil registration system should ensure a holistic approach to legal identity from birth to death.

The identity document as we know it today is a very recent innovation; the shape and size of identity cards were standardized almost fifty years ago. Many countries introduced national identification cards as a way to provide citizens with a standardized form of identification. These cards often included biometric data, such as photographs and fingerprints. Technological advancements led to the development of smart cards and biometric identification, making identification more secure and efficient. These methods began to be widely used for national identity purposes.

Digitalising identity systems

Digital identity aims to transform the public service delivery mechanism in an effective way to accelerate access to the services and reduce the costs of delivering these services [Grassi et al. \(2017\)](#). The ID Lifecycle has four main steps: Registration, Issuance, Use and Management [World Bank Group \(2019\)](#). When developing a digital identity system, we should ensure each step is usable, secure, private and maintainable. Throughout the transformation of this lifecycle with digital technology, new

models of partnerships and frameworks between governments and the private sectors have been established to provide trustworthy digital layers on top of existing legal ID systems. Two main approaches appear to build the main structure: Centralized and Federated. A centralized model builds on a single authority that provides proof of a legal ID. In a federated mechanism, multiple entities provide a digital ID, which is coordinated through a federation authority.

Over the last two decades, hardware and software developments in ICT (e.g., www, cloud services, biometric services, blockchain) have continually improved ID-based services in terms of usability, accessibility and security [Council of Europe \(2023\)](#). As Internet usage has grown, the need for more sophisticated identity and access management systems became evident. An ID infrastructure shares a similar infrastructure with any digital service. But, it should be secure by design as it stores and processes personal, sensitive data. As part of efforts to provide a more secure service, biometric authentication methods such as fingerprint scanners and facial recognition gained prominence [OIX \(2022\)](#). These technologies improved security and user convenience, making them integral components of modern digital ID systems. Another response to the increasing sophistication of cyberattacks, multi-factor authentication gained widespread adoption. In parallel to these developments in the user-side of the cybersecurity concerns, databases and server-side processes have been advanced with different security and privacy-preserving methods. Further, the proliferation of smartphones led to a shift in digital identity access. We explored the ubiquitous features and how to securely enable the use of these internet-connected devices. These changes also affected the database management systems and managing the infrastructure of large-scale digital ID systems to work in real time. Distributed file systems and data processing technologies enabled the efficient storage and analysis of vast amounts of identity data.

LLMs and the digital ID tech stack

As readers notice, the tech stack of the ID management infrastructure is massive and rapidly developing to advance cybersecurity protections and usability. We can define three layers in this tech stack:

- Core (essential) technologies: These technologies build the essential mechanisms in the digital ID system. Database services, authentication management, front-end services and communication protocols are essential services that build a digital ID system securely.
- Supportive (optional) mechanisms: These technologies improve the usability and security both for the citizens and other parties. For example, biometric technologies are a common approach to improving the security and usability of ID-based services.
- Innovation accelerators: These technologies accelerate the discussion and motivate researchers and practitioners to bring change to the landscape. For example, blockchain brought different ideas to build a decentralized environment. Today, we see the same effect with the rise of generative AI, specifically LLMs.

Throughout this transformation process, integrating ML-powered services has served as a supporting mechanism (e.g. computer vision techniques in biometrics, anomaly detection from log analysis). Feature extraction and prediction algorithms have been extensively utilized in biometrics applications, while generative applications have played a crucial role in the process. For instance, the use of synthetic data to mitigate bias is a common approach. Nowadays, generative AI techniques, specifically LLMs, are revolutionizing the innovation landscape. Organizations from both the public

and private sectors are redefining their innovation strategies and collaborating to shape the future around this emerging trend. However, unlike other domains, we have not witnessed the same level of acceleration of innovation in the digital identity field.

Applying LLMs in digital identity systems

Following the ID4D reports, we identified some shared issues in the African context. Considering these current needs of the ID landscape and the capabilities of LLMs, we can anticipate some potential use cases for LLMs to accelerate the discussion in the field. Here, we suggested six potential use cases of LLMs in the foundational identity domain:

1. **Using LLMs for insight generation:** Developing a solution for a multi-partner ecosystem requires taking input from various partners (e.g., government initiatives, NGOs, private sector partners) in multiple formats (e.g., reports, data, standards and guidelines). For example, in the writing process of this section, we read sixteen country-specific reports to identify issues in identity space. Considering the existing LLM capabilities, we can use LLMs to capture information from multiple documents with back-traceability to accelerate a trustworthy insight generation process.
2. **Understanding the potential conflicts before the field-wide implementation:** One key challenge revolves around the concept of "identification" itself, which can sometimes become a source of conflict. Different stakeholders may have varying perspectives and interests, leading to debates and disagreements regarding the scope, criteria, and implications of identification processes. For example, in Cote d'Ivoire, after the coup, the identity issue has become a tension point between different stakeholders. We can use LLMs for social media and newspaper analysis to identify the relevant topics that might affect the identity scene.
3. **Accelerating the legislative regulations:** Another challenge stems from the limitations within legislative regulations governing identification systems. Existing laws and regulations may fail to adequately cover all relevant issues, leaving gaps or ambiguities that can hinder the effective implementation and operation of the systems. LLMs with translation and structured knowledge-creation capabilities can enhance the law-making process by presenting a bouquet of regulations from different countries.
4. **Enhancing inclusivity of the registration and authentication processes:** Individuals with disabilities, those from low socioeconomic backgrounds, and marginalized communities struggle more to achieve identification when compared to the other population groups. Especially LLMs in low-resource languages can increase the accessibility of identity registration and authentication capabilities by offering multimodal remote support.
5. **Accelerating the digitalization of the physical records:** Many identification systems still rely on physical centres for the registration and maintenance of ID records. This dependency on centralized locations can create logistical challenges, particularly in remote or underserved areas, where access to these centres may be limited or impractical. The use of multimodal LLMs can increase the speed of digitalization by requiring minimum human assistance through the process.
6. **Reducing costs through all steps in the ID lifecycle:** A recent survey from ID4D that involves fifteen countries at various levels of ID development and with diverse ecosystems reveals that 90% of the typical cost of ID systems consists of six main categories. From high to low share,

these six main categories are (1) human resources (35-65%), (2) credentials (10-40%), (3) central IT infrastructure (6-15%), (4) physical establishments (3-7%), (5) registration infrastructure (5-20%), and (6) information and education campaigns (3-5%) [World Bank Group \(2019\)](#). LLMs can bring effective solutions in human resources and related costs while making the overall system more inclusive for the citizens.

The potential solutions presented in this paper are defined solely in consideration of the issues stated in ID4D reports that directly impact real-world problems in the domain. If we evaluate the use of LLMs in the core infrastructure of digital ID, we can also argue that it will have a significant impact on developer productivity by, for example, co-piloting the coding process, analyzing security logs, and structuring database logs. However, these secondary uses of LLMs are outside the scope of this paper.

Risks and pitfalls of integrating LLMs into digital identity systems

As we elaborated in the potential use cases, LLMs are powerful tools that hold significant promise in the digital ID domain. However, along with their potential benefits, there are substantial risks and potential pitfalls associated with their use [Kaddour et al. \(2023\)](#). Below, we listed the risks inherent in applying LLMs to digital ID systems:

- **Bias and Fairness:** Similar to any neural architecture, LLMs are not immune to bias [Gallegos et al. \(2023\)](#). They may inadvertently perpetuate and amplify existing biases present in the data they are trained on, leading to unfair treatment and discrimination [Birhane et al. \(2021\)](#); [Feng et al. \(2023\)](#). It can be particularly problematic for the second potential use case when researchers and policymakers use LLMs to identify potential conflicts in the identity domain using social media data or reports.
- **Hallucination:** LLMs can generate text that is not based on factual data and convince readers that the given information is true [Ji et al. \(2023\)](#). This can be a problem in the digital ID domain, where it is used for policy-making. Although there is an array of work reducing the hallucinations, it is important to have a human review of LLM-generated text to ensure that it is accurate and reliable.
- **Evaluation benchmarks** Evaluating language models poses a challenge due to their wide variety of capabilities in different tasks. A model may excel at solving a benchmark problem effortlessly, but a minor alteration to the problem or even a simple change in the prompt can yield contrasting results [Lu et al. \(2022\)](#).
- **Privacy:** The training data of LLMs might contain some Personally Identifiable Information (PII) and API keys, which can appear when generating responses [Carlini et al. \(2021\)](#). In the identity domain, this poses a significant risk to individuals and organizations as most of the information is sensitive in this context.
- **Knowledge Cutoff:** LLMs have a knowledge cutoff, meaning they are not up-to-date with the latest information or developments [Yao et al. \(2023\)](#). In the rapidly evolving digital ID landscape, outdated information could lead to flawed decision-making.
- **Computational power requirements and cost:** Another potential pitfall is the significant processing power required to run LLMs efficiently [Sorscher et al. \(2023\)](#). These models demand substantial computational resources, including powerful GPUs and extensive memory. Although

one of our potential use cases of LLMs is reducing costs, this requirement can lead to high operational costs, making LLM deployment impractical for some organizations. Additionally, limited access to sufficient computational resources could create disparities in the ability to implement LLM-powered digital ID systems.

- **Unidentified attack vectors:** Similar to any other software, LLMs are open to attacks, however, their attack vectors are not adequately identified as the progress in the field is rapidly increasing. Although there are considerable efforts (e.g. MITRE ATLAS [MITRE \(2023\)](#)) to overcome these attacks in a systematic way, the number of adversaries is also increasing with the growing popularity of the field.
- **Knowledge Retrieval Architecture:** When we use LLMs for extracting information from web pages and documents, we can use different retrieval architectures [Langchain \(2023\)](#). The structure of the document and choice of retrieval architecture can significantly impact the performance of LLMs. Inconsistent configurations may lead to unaligned behaviours and unreliable results in digital ID applications.

Despite these challenges, as we elaborated in this paper, LLMs have the potential to revolutionize the ID4D domain. By automating tasks, improving accuracy, and reducing costs, LLMs can help to make digital IDs more accessible and secure for everyone. In conclusion, the effective use of LLMs can present direct solutions for the reported and known issues in the field of ID. In this short paper, we have briefly explained these issues reported by ID4D, and the potential use cases and the pitfalls of LLMs to resolve them.

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